

Restart Project's Data Work with ACTION

Final Report

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Contents

Contents	2
Introduction	4
Who is The Restart Project?	4
Intro to the project	4
Project objectives	4
Project plan	5
1. Update the environmental data we use to calculate the potential CO2e emission savings from repair. (Milestone 2)	5
2. Run online microtasks designed to improve our data on common product faults. (Milestone 3)	5
3. Collaborations & partnerships	5
Overview of Methodology	6
Data & development planning (Milestone 1)	6
Environmental data (Milestone 2)	6
Microtasks (Milestone 3)	8
PrintCat	9
TabiCat	10
BattCat	10
Analysis & dissemination of results (Milestone 4)	10
Environmental data	10
Microtasks	11
Results and Learnings	12
Environmental data	12
Project participation	14
Microtasks	14
PrintCat	14
TabiCat	15
BattCat	15
Task participation	16
Task design	18
Next steps	19

Introduction

Who is The Restart Project?

[The Restart Project](#) manages a global network of voluntary groups (mostly in Europe) who help their local communities repair broken products, preventing pollution in production and disposal.

Intro to the project

Our project addresses the global dimensions of pollution and consumerism, the impacts of our take-make-throw economy. Many imported goods have really short lifespans, which we try to extend at our community repair events. Around 80% of a small electronic device's carbon footprint is emitted before it even reaches European shores. What if we can't use stuff for longer by fixing it? What if these products are impossible to repair by design? What are the real environmental impacts of this, on people on the other side of the planet?

Every device we buy comes with a hidden environmental cost. Understanding this hidden cost is crucial to learning just how green repair is, so we wanted to reveal the true environmental impact of the products we buy and learn from our existing data what measures can make repair more accessible.

Project objectives

- Focus our community on collaborative analysis of products with a high pollution and climate change impact in production, the results of which will be used for ongoing impact evaluation work, and potential for policy influence
- Using our own stuff as an object of analysis, build literacy and engagement on the "invisible" pollution impacts in production among repair activists and supporters that will power this work into the future.
- Include partners from across Europe in our citizen science work which started in the UK

Project plan

We planned to focus on two strands of activity, working with volunteers from our community as citizen scientists:

1. Update the environmental data we use to calculate the potential CO₂e emission savings from repair. (Milestone 2)

In 2014 we first developed our Fixometer tool for community repair groups to calculate the potential CO₂e emission savings from repair using lifecycle assessment (LCA) data we found on a range of consumer electronics. While the tool has served us well, the source data we found was very limited and has aged considerably. Our aim was to expand and update this source data by finding new LCA data for more products across more categories and for more recent products. We then planned to combine these into a single dataset, assess the quality of the data and update the Fixometer. This should allow community groups to more accurately estimate their impact for a wider range of repairs.

2. Run online microtasks designed to improve our data on common product faults. (Milestone 3)

We realised that not only can we use our community data to measure our environmental impact but also to advocate for more repairable products and pro-repair policies: by analysing the data we record, we learn more about why products break and how companies could make them easier to fix. Before starting our work with ACTION, we had already run a small number of experimental quests/microtasks, which became a useful proof-of-concept.

After identifying relevant policy processes being planned at the EU level, we planned to run three new microtasks, each focused on analysing data about certain categories of device in the Fixometer (our community-powered database of repair attempts) relevant to an area of potential upcoming legislation. The hope was that the results of these microtasks would allow us to submit citizen-sourced evidence to policy consultations and provide a counterweight to the sometimes dubious data offered by industry bodies.

3. Collaborations & partnerships

We planned to ask for help with both of these areas of work, engaging our existing community online through our platform and newsletter, and the general public through social media. We hoped to provide an easy way for people to help us, allowing them to commit as much or as little time as they chose, especially on the microtasks.

Our partners in the Open Repair Alliance (ORA) also agreed to help promote these microtasks to their members, opening up our work to a new audience in Europe.

Overview of Methodology

Data & development planning (Milestone 1)

Initially we focused on planning the work required and reviewing our data infrastructure and policies.

Our project mentor, Esteban, introduced us to the concept of a formal Data Management Plan and we worked closely with him to write two such plans, one for our environmental data and a second for our microtask data. Esteban encouraged us to publish [these DMPs on the Argos platform](#), which we did (after helping the Argos team identify a bug in their software). This was a fascinating process that opened our eyes to new ways of sharing our data. We generally license our data as Creative Commons Attribution Share Alike 4.0 International, which we chose again for both datasets in this project. But traditionally we have relied on interested parties finding our data through our own platforms and websites; we hadn't previously considered the possibility of using Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) to share our data more widely and in this more universal way. We are now considering ways to use our datasets as a form of outreach to more specialised audiences.

At this stage, we also began scheduling the software development work required to build the microtask activities using the project management tool Jira. Our team had started working with an Agile Coach (a consultant specialised in [agile software development](#)) to streamline our development process. These microtasks proved to be an excellent opportunity to shape our process and build working practices that can now benefit other areas of our development work, such as building and maintaining our wider community platform.

Finally, we began planning for the recruitment of volunteers and participants using our community platform, email lists and social media (Twitter, Facebook and Instagram). We documented this in our [participant recruitment strategy](#).

Environmental data (Milestone 2)

We worked on updating the data we use to calculate the environmental impact of repairs carried out at community repair events. This data was initially put together in 2014, and things have changed a lot since then, for example the average laptop is significantly lighter than it used to be.

By calculating the embodied environmental impact of products we see at repair events, we can show how much CO₂ emissions are diverted from landfill by extending the life of devices through repair. Our assumption is that the repaired device delays the purchase of a new replacement, displacing part of the impact of producing an additional device.

We recruited six citizen scientists by reaching out to our community and approaching individuals and organisations we thought might be interested. This targeted approach

was suggested to us in the first ACTION inclusion and diversity call, and helped us put together a team that included a broad range of people, some with an established interest in this work (such as a Masters student), others were entirely new to the topic. While we had some interest on most channels, we quickly found that the six people who committed fully all found out about this work through our community forum.

With our online volunteer citizen scientists, we scoured the internet for data that could tell us about the carbon impacts of the products we see at community repair events, such as smartphones and toasters.

We focused on sourcing Lifecycle Assessment (LCA) data and Product Carbon Footprint (PCF) reports. Manufacturers, academics and consultancy firms use these reports to measure the environmental impacts of products. We were most interested in how much greenhouse gas is produced at each stage of a product's life, measured as CO₂ equivalent (CO₂e).

This data proved to be difficult to find. There is a real lack of publicly-available data for many kinds of products, especially common household devices such as kettles and vacuum cleaners. We even approached a number of manufacturers and brands, including LG, HP, Canon and Miele for this data directly. Most didn't respond to us and those that did couldn't help.

However, we were eventually able to find data on nearly 500 products across a wide range of product categories. Unfortunately, all of this data came in PDF format. One of our volunteers was able to write scripts to automatically extract some data from some PDF documents, but for the majority of documents, we had to extract the relevant data manually. The companies who provided this data that we approached were unable or unwilling to provide the data in a machine-readable format.

Ultimately we used this data to produce estimated average weight and embodied CO₂e values for 59 categories of consumer product, up from the 35 in the previous version.

Due to the variety of our data sources, we classified the technical representativeness, recency and reliability of each individual report to produce a data quality index score for every product included in the final calculations. We present this in addition to a data availability score for each category of product alongside our overall findings. This should help people interested in this data understand its limitations.

Compared to the previous version of this data, we increased both the level of data quality and data availability for 83% of the original 35 product categories by at least one rank.

[This data is published here.](#)

Microtasks (Milestone 3)

We collect data at community events about the broken products we see. But the raw data needs to be analysed to become strong evidence for us to present to policy makers in our demand for better products.

As planned, we developed three online microvolunteering tasks with the support of ACTION: PrintCat, TabiCat and BattCat. These took the data in our Fixometer database combined with data from our partners the Open Repair Alliance and asked volunteers to help categorise it. We promoted the tasks across our own channels and our partner organisations also agreed to share them with their own communities. ACTION also provided comms support to help amplify the message.

All of these tasks followed a similar pattern, although we amended and improved each task as we went along, based on feedback from participants and ACTION. [Read the full report of this process here.](#)

Each task focused on a different category of product and we presented participants with details about a device that was brought to a repair event that could not be fixed on the day. PrintCat focused on printers, TabiCat on tablets and e-readers and BattCat on battery problems in any small, battery-powered device. Participants were then asked to categorise the problem from a list of options. **Each device record was shown to two or three different people to ensure the categorisation's accuracy.**

This is what the microtasks looked like:

PrintCat STATUS ABOUT

Simply read the information about the broken printer and select the type of fault described from the list underneath. [Learn more](#)

Source: Repair Cafe Wales | End of life

Printer turns on but ink cartridge stuck in middle Translate

WHERE IS THE MAIN FAULT?

Suggestions

Ink cartridge | Paper feed | Paper output

Card reader | Configuration | Control buttons | Display panel | External damage | Imaging unit/drum | Internal damage | Power supply/connectors

Print quality | Printhead cleaning | Printhead failure | Scanner | Software issue/update | Toner | USB port/cable | Vendor lock-in

Waste toner/ink box | WIFI | Other | Unknown

I don't know, fetch another repair

Powered by data from: **OPEN REPAIR ALLIANCE**

Microtask #1: PrintCat

BattCat: categorise battery problems

STATUS ABOUT

1

Read the information about the broken device.

A volunteer tried to fix this device at a community repair event and wrote this description.

Device: Vacuum Brand: Black & Decker Status: End of life

Description of problem:
Batterijen zijn op, hoe krijg ik dit open

Translate

2

What prevented this device from being repaired?

Select the option that best fits the problem described above.

Battery is not the main problem

Battery not readily available

Built-in or soldered battery, cannot remove

Charger not readily available

Damaged while replacing battery

Difficult to remove battery

New battery too expensive

Unrepairable corrosion or leakage

Other

Poor data

I don't know →

Our progress

The percentage of devices we have classified so far

81.8%

Powered by data from:

OPEN REPAIR ALLIANCE

Microtask #3: BattCat

PrintCat

Our first microtask with ACTION was PrintCat, which we launched on Earth Day (22/04/2021). We had collected information on over 800 broken printers and asked participants to help categorise them.

Printers are an emotive topic for many and after announcing PrintCat on our community forum, the activity received quite a lot of attention across our channels and prompted lots of fascinating conversations about printer design as well as plenty of feedback on the task itself from participants. Our [main forum topic about PrintCat](#) is a good example of this rich interaction.

Thanks to this feedback, we realised that the way we had designed and framed PrintCat in our communications left some participants a little unclear about the nature and purpose of the microtask. The key learning was that many people found the variable quality of the source data frustrating, especially those less familiar with our work. This was a valuable lesson, which we tried to learn from for the following microtasks.

Our partner organisations, Repair Café International based in the Netherlands and Anstiftung based in Germany also played an important role by sharing PrintCat with their communities.

TabiCat

Building on what we learned from PrintCat, we next looked at tablets and ebook readers in a microtask started on the 3rd of June 2021. TabiCat combined data on over 900 broken devices and asked participants to classify them by the type of fault.

As with PrintCat, we continued to receive useful feedback from participants, which we incorporated into our plans for BattCat where possible. However, TabiCat did reach fewer people overall (more on this later).

BattCat

Our final microtask was our most ambitious. Batteries are such a common problem that we have now got data on 1000 devices brought to repair events that stopped working because the battery failed. BattCat launched on the 19th of July 2021.

BattCat also reached fewer people than PrintCat, but those who did participate contributed many more opinions on average.

Following feedback we received during an ACTION interim update meeting about making better use of community gatekeepers to reach more potential participants (i.e. adopt a more grassroots, less top-down approach), we decided to delay the closure of these tasks in order to allow more time for our partners based in the Netherlands and Germany to work with their communities to encourage participation. This was particularly important for the records in Dutch and German, which made up the majority of unclassified records.

In addition, we organised an online social event for our own community to help boost participation and reach those who prefer a more social approach or were less confident about trying the activity on their own. This was another useful suggestion from an ACTION engagement & diversity call.

Analysis & dissemination of results (Milestone 4)

We are starting to process and share the results from our work. This will primarily be through educational tools, written materials and online events.

Environmental data

We are currently working on updating the environmental impact calculations we use on the Fixometer with the new environmental impact data we've sourced and processed. Once complete, this will improve the accuracy of the calculations we provide to community groups when estimating the quantity of CO₂e and e-waste diverted by their repair events on our online platform Restarters.net. We are also consulting our community about the best way to implement these changes: do we retroactively adjust the calculations for their existing repair data or opt to use the new calculations only for

repair data added after we make the change? It is important for us that the community has a say in this decision and this conversation is still ongoing.

Due to our success in finding data on a wider range of products than originally anticipated, we are additionally expanding the range of product categories covered by the calculations and the platform as a whole. This is a long-request feature by many in our community and should help make the tool more useful for volunteers on the ground. It will also align the Fixometer more closely with the Open Repair Data Standard (ORDS), which we help maintain.

However, this has introduced additional technical complexity to the process of updating our tool. Adding new categories has required us to revisit all the data already in the database (around 20,000 records) and recategorise any products belonging to the newly added categories. For example, we are adding 'Coffee maker' as a new category. But historically, these devices had been classified as 'Small kitchen item'. And so, we have had to find all the coffee makers in the database and change their classification to the new 'Coffee maker' category. We are repeating this process for the following new categories: Coffee maker, Iron, Sewing machine, Watch/clock, Games console, Hand tool and Jewellery.

These re-categorisations would affect the current stats for many of the community groups using our software. Therefore we also need to take the time to consult with our community to make sure they agree to this process before we implement these changes.

Only after this work is completed can we update our calculations with the new data. As a result, we were unable to complete this work by our original target of 27/08/2021. We are now aiming to have completed the technical side of this work by 03/09/2021.

As part of our messaging about the new calculations, we will be running a webinar on the 2nd of September with friend-of-Restart, Jessika Richter from The International Institute for Industrial Environmental Economics at Lund University. During the session, we plan to introduce the concept of lifecycle analysis, tell the story of the work we have done, present some of our findings and take questions.

Microtasks

The goal for the microtasks was to be able to extract useful insights for each of the product categories analysed, to be used in conversations and in official policy processes with relevant stakeholders.

The timeline of policy development is always rather tentative - as priorities of legislators change beyond our control. Here is how the three microtasks fit within ongoing policy processes:

- Printers: we launched PrintCat while the European Right to Repair Campaign was preparing for an action to raise awareness about the European Commission's [lack of action](#) on this product category. This gave us an opportunity to also inform

people taking part in PrintCat about what's currently at stake: manufacturers proposing to focus only on professional, expensive printers for repairability, while not even committing to making spare parts available for printers below €350. There is currently no open consultation on printers at UK or EU level, but our activities have contributed to bringing new urgency on this issue. The proposal from manufacturers is likely to be refused, and we will be able to use results from PrintCat when reaching out to policymakers for follow-ups.

- Tablets: at the end of June we attended the first “ecodesign consultation forum” dedicated to discussing a draft European regulation on smartphones and tablets. During that occasion we were already able to contribute data from our ongoing analysis - mostly on how common smartphones and tablets are at community repair events within our networks. We've since submitted evidence to the team working on this regulation, and we will continue to do so in the next few months - hopefully leading up to the approval of an ambitious regulation for this product category. Our experience submitting evidence during a public event with stakeholders from industry was telling: [as we documented](#) in our community forum, we were able to use insights from our data to counter the (very questionable!) argument from industry that most spare parts are not needed by repairers.
- Batteries: the EU Parliament is working on a Directive on batteries. As part of this, with European policy partners we've identified an opportunity to advocate for a clause requiring manufacturers to make user-replaceable batteries for all consumer products to be sold in Europe. Votes on this potential future measures will take place towards the end of the year. In collaboration with partners, we are going to use emerging insights from BattCat alongside research they've commissioned about professional repairers' experience with battery replacement, to make the case for user replaceability of all batteries.

While the final analysis of the results of the microtasks is still ongoing, we're also planning to share complete results with partners of the European Right to Repair campaign with a workshop in coming weeks. This will help reinforce campaign priorities, and give them evidence to inform their messaging, putting more pressure on policymakers. We will document our learnings with a final blog post on this.

Results and Learnings

Environmental data

We collected data on 1406 products. From these, we extracted CO2e data on 491 products and product weight data on 824 products (much of the source data did not contain relevant CO2e or product weight data). The categories of product were based on those defined in the [Open Repair Data Standard \(ORDS\)](#), with the addition of a few unpowered product categories.

We found that for most devices we see at community repair events, the biggest carbon impact occurs before the device is switched on for the first time. That's because for many products, extracting raw materials and manufacturing are very carbon intensive processes.

Medium-sized laptops are the most common device we see at repair events. We found data about 64 models of these laptops from Apple, Dell, HP, Lenovo and Microsoft. And learned that an average laptop of this size represents a lot of CO₂ - about 260 kg - before it's ever used.

That's the equivalent of a flight from London to Berlin and around 81% of the total CO₂e each device produces over its entire life. For most of these laptops, the manufacturer assumed a lifespan of just 4 years. By replacing laptops so often, the emissions start to add up really quickly. Instead, if we use the device for longer, the lower the CO₂e impact will be over time in comparison, as illustrated by the graphs below:

(These graphs were designed after—and inspired by—attending ACTION’s Data visualisation webinar. The reminder to tell a story with data viz was very timely!)

During this process, we discovered a real lack of publicly-available data for many kinds of products. Manufacturers have very few incentives or requirements to perform or publish this type of analysis for their products. As a result many manufacturers simply don’t produce them, especially for common household products like toasters and kettles. Some companies do collect this information, but only a small number actually make them available to the public.

We even approached a number of manufacturers and brands for this data directly. Most didn’t respond to us and those that did couldn’t help. This proved to be a real issue and means our data in these areas is not as robust as for other types of product (such as laptops and smartphones).

Project participation

We worked with a group of 6 highly engaged citizen scientists to complete this research. Our targeted recruitment approach combined with a more general call to action to our core community seemed to work well, as we formed a cohesive, yet diverse group of volunteers. We coordinated our work at informal weekly project meetings followed by individual desk research and data analysis. This format worked well, providing a social element as well as plenty of time for self-directed work. We would likely replicate this approach for future work of this nature with the potential addition of an expert contributor to offer insights and support (this would have saved us some time in the early stages of the project).

Microtasks

For the three tasks, more than 300 people submitted over 6,500 opinions about 2,000 devices. This has given us a better understanding of the data we hold on these different categories of devices.

PrintCat

PrintCat contained 831 records from our Fixometer database; each record represents a device that was brought to a community repair event and the data was input by members of our network or our partners in the Open Repair Alliance.

Around 286 people participated in PrintCat overall. And in total, participants submitted 2392 opinions, reaching the maximum number of opinions for 771 device records. Of these records, 658 reached a consensus opinion and the remaining 113 records had split opinions, requiring adjudication. Logged-in community members submitted an average of 48 opinions each. Anonymous participants submitted an average of 5 opinions per session.

Prior to adjudication, which is ongoing, the top five reported faults were:

1. Paper feed

2. Ink cartridge
3. Printhead cleaning
4. Power supply/connectors
5. Printhead failure

The most common opinion submitted was 'unknown', reinforcing feedback from users about the often poor quality of the source data.

TabiCat

TabiCat contained 941 records. Around 84 people contributed 1870 opinions in total, reaching the maximum number of opinions for 644 records. Of these records, 553 reached a consensus opinion and 91 records had split opinions, requiring adjudication. Logged-in community members submitted an average of 40 opinions each. Anonymous participants submitted an average of 19 opinions per session.

Prior to adjudication, which is ongoing, the top five reported faults were:

1. Screen
2. Power/battery
3. USB/charging port
4. Help/configuration
5. Performance

To address user frustration about low quality data, we added a 'poor data' button in TabiCat, allowing users to flag records that didn't contain enough information to give an opinion. We also worked to remove more of this data before launching the microtask. 'Poor data' was the third most common submission.

BattCat

BattCat was the largest microtask, containing 1000 records. Around 76 participants contributed 2405 opinions, reaching the maximum number of opinions for 858 records. Of these records, 725 reached a consensus opinion and 133 records had split opinions, requiring adjudication. Logged-in community members submitted an average of 72 opinions each. Anonymous participants submitted an average of 20 opinions per session.

Prior to adjudication, which is ongoing, the top reported next steps for **repairable** devices were:

1. Replace with new battery
2. Replace the charger or charging cable
3. Battery is not the main problem
4. Fix the charging port
5. Other

The top reported barriers to repair for **end of life** devices (again, prior to adjudication) were:

1. Battery is not the main problem
2. Other

3. Unrepairable corrosion or leakage
4. Difficult to remove battery
5. Built-in or soldered battery, cannot remove

For repairable devices, 'poor data' was the second most common submission and for end of life devices, it was the most common. This again reflects the need to support community groups to record more detail when capturing this data at repair events.

Task participation

In total, up to 446 people participated in these microtasks. However, this figure (the sum of the number of unique participants in each microtask) is likely an overestimate. This is because we were unable to track anonymous participants between each microtask. It is likely that a significant number of people participated in more than one microtask and so would be double-counted in this total figure.

In general, we saw a trend towards fewer but increasingly engaged participants over time. The first task, PrintCat, reached the most people with each participant contributing an average of 8 opinions. In contrast, BattCat (the final task) reached the fewest people with each participant contributing an average of 32 opinions.

PrintCat reached the highest number of participants of all three microtasks, which we think can be attributed to a few factors:

- The topic was very accessible (who hasn't had a bad experience with a printer?)
- The timing worked well: we launched the task for Earth Day in May, which allowed it to 'ride the Earth Day wave' on social media.
- Our partners (Repair Café International based in the Netherlands, and Anstiftung based in Germany) promoted PrintCat to their communities too, meaning that records in Dutch and German received more attention. (These were the most common languages in the source data after English).
- The concept was new for most of our audience, giving PrintCat a sense of novelty.

However, the level of engagement from the majority of participants was extremely low, with anonymous users contributing just 5 opinions in an average session.

TabiCat and BattCat saw lower numbers of participants. While this was disappointing, we believe there were a number of factors behind this:

- Although we tried to make our communications as accessible as possible, the topics of TabiCat and BattCat perhaps had a less broad appeal; it's likely fewer people have experienced the same frustrations with tablets as with printers, and talking about 'battery powered devices' may have sounded quite technical to those less familiar with our work.
- Both tasks launched in summer months and neither was attached to a wider event in the way that PrintCat was linked to Earth Day. This may have resulted in the microtask feeling less topical.
- For TabiCat and BattCat, the vast majority of records that didn't receive any submissions were in Dutch. While we did provide a translation feature, the extra

friction this added to the UX of the microtasks likely put off many in our audience and community (the vast majority of whom do not speak Dutch). We ought to have worked more closely with our Dutch partner to support their outreach efforts - although they were less active and able to collaborate during the summer. And in future, we can also consider machine-translating all records straight away (although many records are written in abbreviated or colloquial language that automated translation software can find difficult to handle).

Participants per microtask

Even though the number of participants fell from task to task, we were encouraged that the level and quality of engagement rose at the same time, which ensured we still received enough submissions to be able to draw conclusions from the results:

Opinions submitted per microtask

Average number of submissions per participant

We believe that the overall increase in levels of engagement from task to task can be attributed to the following factors:

- Allowing users to report poor data and our UX design work made interacting with tasks easier.
- Our communications became a little more precise to avoid setting up unrealistic expectations for people unfamiliar with our work. This may have made the microtask seem less appealing to some people, but meant that those who did click through were better-prepared for the activity.
- We ran an online event for our community, which focused on BattCat. The event was well attended and allowed people to engage with the task and the team more in-depth in a live, social atmosphere.

Task design

Our main learnings about the design of microtasks are captured [here](#).

In summary, the feedback reinforced our view that User Experience (UX) is crucial to the success of asking people to participate in this kind of task. Our key takeaways are:

- i) Accessibility is essential to ensure participants understand what we are asking of them, no matter what their prior knowledge of the subject.
- ii) Encouraging feedback and making sure there were spaces for users to discuss the tasks. This made sure we knew what was working and what wasn't and could improve each task as we moved forward. It also helped users feel more valued and engaged as we were listening to them.

iii) Prioritising which improvements to implement for each task and which groups of users will benefit from these changes. This project has allowed us to acknowledge that any amendment will change the experience for each user and we need to prioritise which group of users we want to engage.

As discussed, by far the biggest criticism from participants was on the quality of the data. The data is gathered by repairer volunteers at community events, and is often input after the event. This means it is very high level and does not always capture enough information to allow participants to form a comprehensive opinion on how to categorise the device. We addressed this in the progress of these tasks by introducing a button for reporting poor data. However, ultimately we will need to do more to motivate volunteers to input better quality data in the first place, possibly by informing and illustrating how the data is used.

We also learned that the number of participants was highest when our partners felt most confident encouraging their own communities to take part. This was demonstrated by PrintCat, which reached nearly 300 people overall compared to the subsequent tasks, which did not reach as many people in our partners' communities. In future, we need to do more to support partners with communication materials and coordinate activities more closely.

Looking back, the pace of activity we set up was probably a bit too ambitious for our community: if we want to further increase their engagement with the data, it might be best to reduce the number of future microtasks to 2-3 per year, rather than launching 3 within 3 months.

Through our work with our project mentor, Esteban, we have also gained a deeper understanding of how open data can be shared and documented, using citizen science platforms, open data repositories and Digital Object Identifiers. We now hope to expand our use of these resources as a way to give our data greater visibility.

Finally, the rapid software development required to design, code, launch and iterate these microtasks has proved a challenge. But, with guidance from our consultant, this has allowed us to better connect our data work with our software work and develop more structured working practices that we can apply to future projects.

Next steps

Our newly updated environmental impact data and the lessons we have learned from collecting it open up many new possibilities for exciting future projects. We are already investigating the potential of using this data in several new ways:

- Using our data to help model the potential environmental benefits of repair-focused policies, helping to make an even stronger case for the Right to Repair at EU or UK level.

- Developing an API to facilitate easy access to impact calculations for members of the public and a wide range of other NGOs, businesses and public bodies.
- Creating new educational and media resources and expanding on existing ones. For example, one of the most visited pages on our site is: [‘Mobiles: the global footprint’](#). We can now update this and develop new versions for a range of products. We can also work with our community to bring this data into community events.
- Engaging a broader range of community repair groups now that we can support a wider range of product categories (such as unpowered items).

As the ‘EU bubble’ gears back up after the summer, we hope to use the results of our microtask activities to influence upcoming policy decisions in collaboration with the European Right to Repair campaign, as explored earlier.

While the pace of these three microtasks was perhaps too fast, this work has established a methodology for similar citizen science projects going forward, allowing us to make the most of any future opportunities to help shape policy that arise. This type of open data could be enhanced by combining it with our environmental data. Such analysis has the potential not only to show which kinds of policy would have the greatest benefits for repairing certain devices, but also why such a policy is important. Finally, we hope to use any success in this to motivate volunteers on the ground by demonstrating that their work really can make a difference, even at the highest levels.

This work was undertaken as part of the ACTION project.

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